

Rediscovering Valonia Oak Acorns (Evrytania)

www.af4eu.eu

Valonia oak acorn cups (photo by A. Papadopoulos)

The valonia oak systems in Greece are ancient open forests (silvopastoral systems) or agricultural fields with valonia oak trees (agro-silvopastoral system) with particular socio-economic, ecological and cultural value. They support numerous traditional uses (grazing, acorn cups and nuts collection, harvesting timber wood and firewood, charcoal, specific, aromatic and medicinal plants) and provide numerous ecosystem services. Valonia oak forests are one of the habitats of the NATURA 2000 network in Greece with code 9350 and include monumental trees in many places in Greece. In Evritania, individual trees and groups or small stands of valonia oak are found in the lower altitude zone of Western Evritania.

A very important traditional agroforestry activity in valonia oak forests was the harvesting of cups for tannery. Along with grazing, it was the most important economic activity taking place in these forests until the 1970s, contributing significantly to the local economy. The cups were mainly exported abroad as raw material or after processing, as a powder, in liquid form or as an extract for use in tannery. High quality acorn cups may contain up to 20-30% tannin while the scales of the cups may vary between 30-40%. In recent years there has been interest in reusing these systems for oak harvesting, due to the demand for ecological products for use in tannery, yarn dyeing, cosmetology and pharmacology. Lately there is also an increasing demand for the acorn nuts for human consumption and use (flour, oil, extract). Acorn flour is characterized as gluten free with high concentration in proteins, K, Mg, Ca, and B6 vitamin.

The restoration of this activity is considered necessary for ecological, historical and protection reasons of individual oak trees and forests, but also for the retention or restoration of the inhabitants of mountain villages and the development of mountainous areas in the context of sustainable development.

Andreas Papadopoulos

Department of forestry &
Natural Environment Management,
Karpenissi, Greece

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101086563. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.